

Chromium(III), manganese(III), iron(III), oxovanadium(II), zirconium(IV) and dioxouranium(II) complexes of hydrazone of isonicotinic acid hydrazide

P. R. Mandlik, S. R. Aswale and A. S. Aswar*

Department of Chemistry, Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, India

Fax : 91-0721-662135

Manuscript received 21 September 2001, revised 8 March 2002, accepted 5 April 2002

Coordination complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II}, Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{II} with Schiff base derived from 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone and isonicotinic acid hydrazide (HMAIH) have been prepared. The ligand acts as monobasic bidentate, monobasic tridentate and dibasic tridentate depending upon the reaction conditions. The thermal data have been analyzed for the activation energies by Broido's method and obey first order kinetics. The ligand and the complexes have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Derivatives of isonicotinic acid and its hydrazide are well known for their antitubercular activity¹. Hydrazides and hydrazones have interesting ligation properties due to the presence of several potential coordination sites. Metal complexes of aroylhydrazones have broad biological activities². Much work has been done on the Schiff base complexes of isonicotinic acid hydrazide³⁻⁵. However, no work seems to have been reported on the metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from substituted acetophenones and isonicotinic acid hydrazide. Therefore, it was thought of interest to prepare Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III}, VO^{II}, Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{II} complexes of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone isonicotinoylhydrazone (HMAIH).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are coloured solids and stable in air. The complexes except UO₂^{II} are insoluble in water and common coordinating solvents but soluble in

DMF and DMSO. The UO₂^{II} complex is soluble in MeOH, EtOH, DMF and DMSO. The analytical data of the complexes indicate metal-to-ligand ratio as 1 : 2 for the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} complexes, while 1 : 1 for the Mn^{III}, VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes. The conductivity data of the complexes in 10⁻³ M DMF at room temperature (10–28 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) show that they are non-electrolytes.

¹H NMR spectrum of HMAIH shows signal at δ 12.70 (1H, br, phenolic OH), 11.20 (1H, s, imino), 9.00, 8.10 (4H, m, isonicotinic), 7.80, 7.30, 7.10 (3H, m, phenyl-H), 3.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.20 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃). The free ligand exhibits IR bands at 3200 (NH), 2900–2800 (OH), 1666 (C=O), 1611 (C=N) and 1296 cm⁻¹ (phenolic C–O bending). In the spectra of all the complexes, the band due to H-bonded OH of the ligand disappeared, phenolic C–O vibrations appeared at higher frequency by 10–20 cm⁻¹ and azomethine C=N shifted to lower frequency by 10–15 cm⁻¹, indicating

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.	Colour	Metal % Found/(Calcd.)	μ _{eff} B.M.	Λ _m Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹	Dec. temp. °C	E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
						Step I	Step II	Step III
[Cr(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O)(Cl)].H ₂ O	Rust	7.97 (7.88)	4.08	25	445	11.21	30.73	66.43
[Mn(L)(H ₂ O)(OAc)].H ₂ O	Brown	13.23 (14.16)	4.93	19	470	9.79	24.23	53.29
[Fe(LH) ₂ (H ₂ O)(Cl)].H ₂ O	Black	8.48 (8.41)	5.98	23	555	6.13	35.04	62.62
[VO(L)] ₂	Olive	15.55 (15.24)	1.5	10	480	83.04	80.89	–
[Zr(LH) ₂ (OH) ₂].3H ₂ O	Yellow	12.80 (12.74)	Dia	28	565	22.85	31.51	53.41
[UO ₂ (LH)(OAc)]	Orange	40.20 (39.85)	Dia	21	560	26.27	64.02	–

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

coordination of the ligand to metal ion through phenolic oxygen via deprotonation⁶ and coordination of C=N group through nitrogen⁷.

The spectra of the Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} complexes display $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibrations almost at the same frequencies as in the spectra of the free ligand, suggesting keto form of ligand and non-involvement of amide oxygen in the coordination to metal³. It is therefore inferred that the ligand in complexes sl. nos. 1, 3 and 5 coordinates in monobasic bidentate fashion. The spectra of the Mn^{III} and VO^{II} do not show the band due to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ frequencies, indicating the coordination of the ligand to metal in enol form⁸. It is supported by the presence of frequencies of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ enolic and azine (C=N-N=C)¹² in their spectra, indicating the dibasic tridentate nature of the ligand in these complexes.

The UO₂^{II} complex displays the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band at lower frequency by 20 cm⁻¹, indicating the coordination through the amide oxygen atom of the ligand⁹. A strong band at 1550 cm⁻¹ in the ligand spectrum is assigned to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ present in isonicotinic ring of HMAIH. This band is not affected in the spectra of all the complexes¹⁰ indicating non-participation of ring nitrogen atom in coordination. The Mn^{III} and UO₂^{II} complexes show two bands at 1608–1609 and 1401–1412 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{asym} (OCO) and ν_{sym} (OCO). This indicates that acetate ligand coordinates as a monodentate ligand¹¹. The VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes display strong bands at 990 (V=O) and 910 cm⁻¹ (O=U=O). The absence of a new band at 850–950 cm⁻¹ (Zr=O) and the presence of a band¹² at 1153 cm⁻¹ (Zr-OH) favors the formation of [Zr(OH)₂(LH)₂].3H₂O and not [Zr(O)(LH)₂].4H₂O. The presence of coordinated water is suggested by the broad absorption around 3400 cm⁻¹ in the Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes, supported by two bands at 830–780 cm⁻¹ attributed to rocking and wagging modes of coordinated water. The UO₂^{II} complex reveals bands at 597 (U-O) and 505 cm⁻¹ (U-N)⁶. In other complexes, the bands at 500–530 and 410–430 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ vibrations¹³.

The magnetic moments of the Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes show spin-only values. The reflectance spectra of the Cr^{III} complexes exhibit three bands which can be assigned to transitions characteristic of an octahedral geometry around the Cr^{III} ion^{14,15}. The lowest energy spin-allowed transition (ν_1) is ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F). The other two bands at 25470 (ν_2) and 41055 cm⁻¹ (ν_3) are assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) transitions, respectively. The various ligand field parameters have been evaluated for the Cr^{III} complex. The value of first spin-allowed transition (ν_1) at 19215 cm⁻¹ is directly taken as 10 Dq. The value of

Racah parameter B, the nephelauxetic ratio β (B in complex/B in free-ion) and CFSE calculated^{16,17} are found to be 592 cm⁻¹, 0.643 and 229.57 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The Mn^{III} complex showing bands around at 14084, 16950, 20202 and 25641 cm⁻¹ may be assigned respectively to the transitions ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5A_1$, ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5B_2$, ${}^5B_1 \rightarrow {}^5E$ and LMCT¹⁸. The Fe^{III} complex exhibits three bands at 14200, 18280 and 23200 cm⁻¹, assigned respectively to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ ¹⁵. The VO^{II} complex displays bands at 13888, 16949, 22222 and 29411 cm⁻¹, assigned respectively to the transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ and LMCT¹⁹. The Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{II} complexes show a sharp bands at 42000 and 40500 cm⁻¹, respectively, corresponding to CT transitions.

The band assignment and the magnetic moment values of the Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes and diamagnetic nature of the Zr^{IV} and UO₂^{II} complexes are consistent with octahedral geometry, while square-pyramidal geometry in case of the Mn^{III} and VO^{II} complexes.

Thermal studies : Thermogravimetry data reveals that the complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{III}, Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} decompose in three steps, while VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes in two steps. The presence of water molecules (lattice/coordinated) suggested from IR spectra is confirmed by thermogravimetric data. The Cr^{III}, Mn^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes lose their weights in the temperature range 130–230° corresponding to one lattice and one coordinated water molecules. In case of the Zr^{IV} complex, weight-loss at about 130° corresponds to three lattice water molecules. The VO^{II} and UO₂^{II} complexes are stable up to 350 and 300°, respectively, indicating the absence of any water molecules²⁰. The organic moiety decomposed further with increasing temperature. Although decomposed fragments of the ligand could not be approximated owing to continuous weight-loss, the complete decomposition of the ligand occurred at ~560° in all the complexes. At the end of final step, i.e. 600–680°, stable metallic oxides were found. The activation energy for each step was calculated from the Broido²¹ plots of ln(ln 1/y) vs 1/T × 10³. Since the plots are straight-lines, the rate of the reaction is believed to be one over the entire range of decomposition. From the decomposition temperatures (Table 1), the relative thermal stabilities of the complexes were found to be : Zr > UO₂ > Fe > VO > Mn > Cr.

Biological activities : The Zr^{IV} complex was found to be highly active against *E. coli*, *S. typhi* and *Rhizobium*, the Mn^{III} complex showed good activity against *E. coli* and complexes of Cr^{III} and UO₂^{II} showed moderate activity against *E. coli* and *Rhizobium* but weak activity against *S. typhi* organism.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvents were of A.R. grade and used as such. Hydrazide was obtained from E. Merck. 2-Hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone²² and manganese(III) acetate dihydrate²³ were prepared by known methods.

HMAIH : A solution of isonicotinoyl hydrazide (0.005 mol) in ethanol (25 cm³) was added to an ethanolic solution (25 cm³) of 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (0.005 mol) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. then cooled to room temperature. The resulting pale yellow coloured solid was washed with ethanol, crystallized from DMF and dried under reduced pressure at ambient temperature, (yield 70%). m.p. 230°.

Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes : To a hot solution of HMAIH (0.004 mol) in DMF-ethanol (50 cm³; 1 : 4, v/v), a suspension of respective metal chloride in ethanol (0.002 mol) was added dropwise with stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The precipitated complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried over fused calcium chloride, (yields 65–70%).

Mn^{III}, VO^{II}, UO₂^{II} complexes : To a hot solution of HMAIH (0.002 mol) dissolved in DMF-ethanol (25 cm³; 1 : 4, v/v), a suspension of metal ion (acetates of Mn^{III}, UO₂^{II}, vanadyl sulfate) in methanol (0.002 mol) was added dropwise with constant stirring and the mixture was refluxed for 5–6 h. The precipitated complexes were washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried over fused calcium chloride, (yields 60–70%).

Zr^{IV} complex : A methanolic solution of sodium acetate (15 cm³, 0.004 mol) was added to a methanolic solution of zirconyl oxychloride (15 cm³, 0.002 mol) with stirring and the separated NaCl was filtered off. The solution of HMAIH (0.002 mol) in DMF-methanol (40 cm³; 1 : 4, v/v) was then added to it and refluxed for 4 h. The resulting solid was washed with hot water followed by methanol and finally dried over fused calcium chloride (yield 76%).

The metal and chloride were analyzed using standard methods²⁴. All the physical methods used were as reported earlier²⁵. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a EM-360 spectrometer, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 842 spectrophotometer at R.S.I.C., Chandigarh, and diffused reflectance spectra on a Carry 2390 spectrophotometer at R.S.I.C., Chennai. Molar conductance of the complexes at 10⁻³ M dilution in DMF was determined using an Equipronic EQ-660 conductivity meter with a cell constant of 1.00 at room temperature. Magnetic measurement was made on a Gouy balance at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as the

calibrant. Molecular weight was determined by Rast method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prin. V. G. Bhamburkar, Shri Shivaji Science College, Amravati, and University authorities for facilities and also to R.S.I.C., Chandigarh and I.I.T., Chennai, for elemental and spectral recording, respectively. One the authors (P.R.M.) is grateful of U.G.C., W.R.O., Pune, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. P. Sharma, A. K. Kothari and N. K. Sharma, *Indian J. Derm. Vener. Lepr.*, 1995, **61**, 26
2. K. Dey, K. Chakraborty, P. K. Bhattacharya, D. Bandopadhyay, S. K. Nag and R. Bhowmick, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1139
3. R. A. Lal, M. L. Pal, J. Chakraborty and A. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1194.
4. M. Jayaramadu and K. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, **38**, 1173.
5. M. R. Maurya, D. C. Antony, S. Gopinathan, V. G. Puranik, S. S. Tavade and C. Gopinathan, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1995, **68**, 2847.
6. G. M. Shashidhara and T. R. Goudar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 360.
7. S. I. Mostafa, T. H. Rakha and M. M. El-Agex, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 1301
8. M. R. Maurya and C. Gopinathan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 701
9. R. K. Agarwal, H. Agarwal and K. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 605
10. S. Rao and K. H. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 58
11. F. A. El-Saied, M. I. Ayad, R. M. Issa and S. A. Aly, *Pol. J. Chem.*, 2000, **74**, 919.
12. M. R. Maurya and A. Syamal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 836.
13. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1978
14. R. S. Drago, D. W. Meek, M. S. Joesten and L. Laroche, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 124
15. A. M. Karampurwala, A. Ray and R. P. Patel, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1989, **19**, 219.
16. E. Konig, *Struct. Bonding*, 1971.
17. J. D. Lee, "Concise Inorganic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1991.

18. R. Mukhopadhyay, S. Bhattacharjee and R. Bhattacharyya, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1996, **108**, 193.
19. K. B. Gudasi and T. R. Goudar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 346.
20. R. K. Agrawal and J. Prakash, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 2399.
21. A. Broido, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A-2*, 1964, **7**, 1761.
22. G. D. Thorn and R. A. Ludwig, "The Dithiocarbamates and Related Compounds", New York, 1962.
23. O. T. Chistensen, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1901, **27**, 325.
24. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd. ed., ELBS, London, 1961.
25. A. S. Aswar, R. G. Mahale, P. R. Kakade and S. G. Bhadange, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 395.